

Kwoma

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Entered by Emily Pitek, Human Relations Area Files

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Entry tags: Melanesia, Syncretic Religions, Religious Group, Oceanic Religions

The Kwoma inhabit the Peilungua Mountain Range, located northwest of the Sepik River in Papua New Guinea. The Kwoma are comprised of four autonomous sub-tribes: the Tangwishamp, the Urumbanj, the Koriasi, and the Hongwam; this entry focuses specifically on the Hongwam around the time of 1937. At this time, the Hongwam (hereafter referred to as Kwoma) had some contact with outsiders, including the Ambunti Police Post (and therefore the Australian government) which was located on the southeastern slope of Ambunti mountain. However, substantial culture change (including missionary influence) did not take place until after the time this entry focuses on. The Kwoma do not have an official political office; leadership positions are earned through age, knowledge, and ability. Also absent are official religious leaders; religious activities are performed by what ethnographers have named the Yam cult (because of the yam's important connection with rituals and social groups). Membership in the highest section and possession of associated ritual knowledge is reserved exclusively for men who have gained importance in the community by having taken a head during a headhunting raid. Although the Kwoma do not have official political officials or religious leaders, the religious sphere of life is not differentiated from other aspects of life. Therefore, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society itself. A variety of supernatural beings are present, including ghosts and non-human supernatural beings (namely, those known as marsalai). Sorcery plays an important role in explaining sickness and death.

Date Range: 1912 CE - 1937 CE

Region: Ambunti Sub-Province, Sepik River region, Papua New Guinea

Region tags: Oceania, Melanesia, Papua New Guinea

Ambunti Sub-Province of the Sepik River region, Papua New Guinea around the time of 1937. Specifically, the Hongwam subtribe

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research.
- Source 2: Whiting, J.W.M., and Reed, S.W. (Dec., 1938). Kwoma culture: Report on field work in the Mandated Territory of New Guinea. Oceania, 9(2). 170-216.
- Source 3: Murdock, G.P. & Wilson, S.F. (Jul., 1972). Settlement patterns and community organization: Cross-Cultural Codes 3. Ethnology, 11(3), 254-295.

– Source 1: Tuden, A. & Marshall, C. (Oct., 1972). Political organization: Cross-cultural codes 4. *Ethnology*, 11(4), 436-464.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=oj13-001>

– Source 1 Description: Whiting, J. W. M. (1941). *Becoming A Kwoma: Teaching And Learning In A New Guinea Tribe*.

– Source 2 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=oj13-002>

– Source 2 Description: Whiting, J. W. M. (1970). *Kwoma Journal*

– Source 3 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=oj13-000>

– Source 3 Description: Bowden, Ross. 2010. "Culture Summary: Kwoma." New Haven, Conn.: Human Relations Area Files.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: "The first contact [with Europeans] was in 1913 when the Kwoma killed a police boy connected with the Behrmann expedition, for raping one of their women. A Kwoma was shot in reprisal. From this time until the Australians brought them 'under control' in 1928, the Kwoma had little contact with Europeans. Since then they have come only occasionally in touch with white recruiters, traders, missionaries, and Australian government officers" (Whiting, 1941:19). "Up to the present, missionaries have sought greener fields, or possibly a more level terrain, in which to pursue their endeavors. A Catholic catechist of Yambon has been detailed to conduct a weekly lesson among the Hongwam but they have shown themselves indifferent to him (he is a youth of little note even in his own village) and to his feeble attempts to gain their ear" (Whiting and Reed, 1938:175).

Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 1649, Frequency of Internal Warfare (Resolved Rating), originally coded the Kwoma as a 1.75, which is between original code 1 (internal warfare seems to be absent or rare), and 2 (internal warfare seems to occur once every 3 to 10 years). Additionally, SCCS Variable 1654, Pacification, indicates that the society is not completely pacified: some indication that warfare has decreased because of pacification attempts. Source of information: Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004. From this information, it can be inferred that some violent conflict within the sample region is present.

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 1650, Frequency of External Warfare (Resolved Rating), indicates that external warfare seems to occur once ever 3 to 10 years (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved

from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more information regarding the system for assigning religious affiliation.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: "At about the age of puberty [the adolescent boy] is initiated into the first stage of the yam cult. He must first decide whether he wishes to join the yenema or minjama section. Although it is presumably up to him to make this choice, his father, older brothers, and paternal uncles exert considerable pressure upon him. It is their wish to keep the hamlet about equally represented in each section and they therefore see to it that such a balance is maintained by influencing the adolescents who are ready to make their choice" (Whiting, 1941:89).

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: Social (kin) influence

Notes: "At about the age of puberty [the adolescent boy] is initiated into the first stage of the yam cult. He must first decide whether he wishes to join the yenema or minjama section. Although it is presumably up to him to make this choice, his father, older brothers, and paternal uncles exert considerable pressure upon him. It is their wish to keep the hamlet about equally represented in each section and they therefore see to it that such a balance is maintained by influencing the adolescents who are ready to make their choice" (Whiting, 1941:89).

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of new member recruitment.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 1740, Levels of Political Hierarchy, indicates that no formal political office is present (Lang, 1998; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). Additionally, there is no ethnographic evidence that religious leaders are recognized among the Kwoma. "Religious activities are performed by the yam cult. This cult is divided into three sections: Yenama, Minjama, and Nokwi. Every Kwoma boy in the subtribe is elected during adolescence to either Yenama or Minjama; young men of promise are inducted into both sections. Nokwi, the highest stage of the cult, receives only men who are of high prestige and who have taken a head" (Whiting, 1941:12). Although the Kwoma do not have official

political officials or religious leaders, the religious sphere of life is not differentiated from other aspects of life; the religious group is coterminous with the society itself. In this sense, it can be said that the religion has official political support.

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– No

Notes: No official religious leaders (such as priests) are recognized.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 1745, Religio-political overlap, indicates that no formal political office is present (Lang, 1998; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

Notes: No official legal code (religious or polity) is present.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of a conception of apostasy.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 374

Notes: Whiting and Reed (1938:173) estimated the Hongwam subtribe of the Kwoma (which this entry focuses on) to be 374 individuals.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 1740, Levels of Political Hierarchy, indicates that no formal political office is present (Lang, 1998; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). Additionally, there is no ethnographic evidence that religious leaders are recognized among the Kwoma. "Religious activities are performed by the yam cult. This cult is divided into three sections: Yenama, Minjama, and Nokwi. Every Kwoma boy in the subtribe is elected during adolescence to either Yenama or Minjama; young men of promise are inducted into both sections. Nokwi, the highest stage of the cult, receives only men who are of high prestige and who have taken a head" (Whiting, 1941:12).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of scripture among the Kwoma.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: According to Murdock and Wilson, (1972, Column 6: Large or Impressive Structures) "the most impressive structure (or type of structure) is a temple, church, commemorative monument, or other essentially religious or ceremonial edifice." (Note: equivalent to SCCS Variable 66, Large or Impressive Structures.

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of pilgrimages.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "Every living Kwoma is possessed of a soul which is externally visible in the shadow or mirrored reflection. The soul is believed to desert the body during sleep, hence one should neither awaken others roughly nor rise suddenly oneself lest the soul have too little time to return to the body. Besides the soul, every individual has a personal ghost of his own which accompanies him at all times to prevent him from approaching dangerous spots, to fight off dangerous ghosts of other men, and to guard the person against theft of any sorcery material. Death results when this ghost deserts the body. After death the ghost goes to live in the land of the dead" (Whiting and Reed, 1938:214-215).

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: Whiting and Reed, 1938:214-215

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: Whiting and Reed, 1938:214-215

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "After death the ghost goes to live in the land of the dead. Each clan-hamlet owns certain spots in the surrounding country which are reserved as dwelling places for the ancestral ghosts. Here they dwell in a topsy-turvy world where they walk across bodies of water and use canoes for travel on land. During the day they sleep in their invisible hamlets and come out at night to visit and observe their living relatives" (Whiting and Reed, 1938:215).

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more details on the spatial location of the afterlife.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– Yes

Notes: "Each clan-hamlet owns certain spots in the surrounding country which are reserved as dwelling places for the ancestral ghosts. Here they dwell in a topsy-turvy world where they walk across bodies of water and use canoes for travel on land. During the day they sleep in their invisible hamlets and come out at night to visit and observe their living relatives" (Whiting and Reed, 1938:215).

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for a belief in reincarnation.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: "Kwoma culture defines the persons who shall dispose of and mourn for the dead. The relatives of the deceased gather to place his body on a platform where it is exposed for several months. Then the members of the subtribe attend a second funeral, for the ceremonial disposal of the bones, and a feast, after which the adult males celebrate the end of the mourning period at the house tambran with gong, flute, and dance" (Whiting, 1941:14).

↳ Cremation:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cremation.

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of mummification.

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: After lying on an outdoor burial platform for several months, the bones of the deceased are cleaned and interred below ground. "A corpse is allowed to stay on the burial platform for several months...At the end of this time a second funeral is held, and the bones, which are by this time dried and bleached by the weather, are taken from the platform and distributed to friends of the deceased. The best friend gets the mandible, the second best receives the clavicle, and the third best one of the arm bones. The oldest son inherits the femurs, which he may fashion into daggers. The remaining bones are buried under the floor of the house in which the deceased has lived" (Whiting, 1941:143).

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– No

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– Yes [specify]: Dis-articulated bones

Notes: (Whiting, 1941:143)

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cannibalism.

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Notes: Corpses are temporarily (for several months) placed on an outdoor burial platform before being permanently interred below ground. During the initial outdoor burial platform period, the body is somewhat exposed to the elements, but exposure to the elements is not the direct intention of this time. See Whiting, 1941:143 for more details.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of feeding corpses to animals.

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: "A corpse is allowed to stay on the burial platform for several months...At the end of this time a second funeral is held, and the bones, which are by this time dried and bleached by the weather, are taken from the platform and distributed to friends of the deceased. The best friend gets the mandible, the second best receives the clavicle, and the third best one of the arm bones. The oldest son inherits the femurs, which he may fashion into daggers. The remaining bones are buried under the floor of the house in which the deceased has lived" (Whiting, 1941:143).

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– Yes [specify]: Outdoor burial platform

Notes: "A corpse is allowed to lie in the house until a burial platform is built. Early in the morning of the day following the death, the relatives erect near the house of the deceased a covered platform set on stilts about ten feet from the ground. When it is finished, the corpse is placed upon a wooden shield carried by several of the male relatives and lifted to the platform with the aid of a ladder. The body is then washed, and three of the spears of the deceased are placed across the neck, abdomen, and legs and lashed to the floor of the platform to prevent the corpse from falling...a corpse is allowed to stay on the burial platform for several months" (Whiting, 1941:143).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of co-sacrifices in burials.

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of grave goods.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: "A corpse is allowed to stay on the burial platform for several months...At the end of this time a second funeral is held, and the bones, which are by this time dried and bleached by the weather, are taken from the platform and distributed to friends of the deceased. The best friend gets the mandible, the second best receives the clavicle, and the third best one of the arm bones. The oldest son inherits the femurs, which he may fashion into daggers. The remaining bones are buried under the floor of the house in which the deceased has lived" (Whiting, 1941:143).

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

Notes: The bones of the deceased are interred below the house; no evidence for the presence of cemeteries (see Whiting, 1941:143).

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: (Whiting, 1941:143)

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Ghosts are believed to be present among the Kwoma, as well as non-human supernatural beings including those known as marsalai. See questions below for more details.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 238, Religion: high gods [Note: Equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas Column 34], indicates that a high god is absent (Murdock, 1962-1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "Ghosts are believed to be the spirits of dead Kwoma who live on the outskirts of the tribal territory" (Whiting, 1941:204). "Ghost lore is taught during childhood. The child is told that the spirits of the dead live on a mountain at the edge of the tribal territory, where they lead a topsy-turvy existence. They go by canoe on land and walk upon the water; they sleep by day and venture out at night" (Whiting, 1941:55).

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: "Ghosts are believed to be the spirits of dead Kwoma who live on the outskirts of the tribal territory. Either as invisible shadows or in the form of a bird or an animal, they sometimes visit the hamlet of the living, particularly at night or when a death has occurred" (Whiting, 1941:204).

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "If a Kwoma does not express sufficient sorrow for the death of a relative, the ghost of the deceased is likely to become angry and either frighten or possess the unappreciative man or woman. Thus those who are not motivated by personal feelings for the deceased may still mourn to avoid antagonizing his ghost" (Whiting, 1941:143).

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Notes: "During the day they [the ghosts] sleep in their invisible hamlets and come out at night to visit and observe their living relatives" (Whiting and Reed, 1938:215).

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: "If a Kwoma does not express sufficient sorrow for the death of a relative, the ghost of the deceased is likely to become angry and either frighten or possess the unappreciative man or woman. Thus those who are not motivated by personal feelings for the deceased may still mourn to avoid antagonizing his ghost" (Whiting, 1941:143).

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: "When a Kwoma dreams of someone who has died, he is told that the ghost of this person has actually visited him in the night" (Whiting, 1941:208).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "Marsalai are supposed to be huge monsters in the form of snakes or crocodiles which cause rain and wind storms, earthquakes, and other cosmic phenomena. They are supposed to be present at the yam-cult ceremonies and to be responsible for a plentiful yield of this crop" (Whiting, 1941:204).

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "Marsalai are supposed to be huge monsters in the form of snakes or crocodiles which cause rain and wind storms, earthquakes, and other cosmic phenomena. They are supposed to be present at the yam-cult ceremonies and to be responsible for a plentiful yield of this crop" (Whiting, 1941:204). "There are other types of supernatural creatures who dwell in rocks, waterholes, etc., in the guise of snakes. They cause wind, rain, thunder, lightening and the rainbow, and are dangerous to man in that if they are disturbed they will shoot him with a sago needle which is painful but not fatal. These beings are associated with the men's cult" (Whiting, 1970:72).

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of mixed human-divine beings.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: The spirits of deceased humans, as well as non-human supernatural beings are present (Whiting, 1941, various pages including:55, 72, 204).

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– No

Notes: There does not appear to be a particular organization for the Kwoma's supernatural beings.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: "A ghost is believed to possess a person in order to express his anger at a living relative (usually not the possessed person himself) for some sin which he is committing. In order to make the ghost return to the land of the dead, the proper sin must be confessed by an exorcist as spokesman for the group. The exorcist, a relative of the possessed person, lists the sins of the community one by one until the ghost indicates the reason for his anger by means of an affirmation from the possessed person. The sinner then promises to mend his ways, and the ghost returns to the land of the dead" (Whiting, 1941:217).

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– I don't know

Notes: It is unclear if supernatural beings mete out punishment, or if the threat of supernatural punishment is used as a child-rearing technique. Children are told not to go too close to the dwelling places of Marsalai, for if they do, the angry Marsalai will cause a bad storm or shoot an invisible sago needle into the intruder's foot (Whiting, 1941:53). Additionally, children and adolescents are told that they will be attacked by ghosts if they travel outside at night (Whiting, 1941:203). Lastly, it is said that ghosts will frighten or possess someone if they did not express enough sorrow at the deceased's funeral (Whiting, 1941:143).

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of supernatural rewards.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of messianic beliefs among the Kwoma.

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of an eschatology.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for required celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more information regarding taboos on sexual activity.

Monogamy (males):

– No

Notes: "A Kwoma man's sexual behavior is not restricted to intercourse with his wife. He continues to have affairs with other women in a manner similar to that described for adolescents" (Whiting, 1941:126).

Monogamy (females):

– No

Notes: "Every man knows that his wife is probably unfaithful to him, but unless he is extremely jealous he does not spy on her and punishes her only if she is indiscreet enough to be conspicuous" (Whiting, 1941:126).

Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: "A man may not have sexual intercourse with his wife when she is menstruating, lest his penis be damaged by menstrual blood; nor when she is obviously pregnant, lest he damage the foetus; nor when she has an infant still at the breast, lest she have a second child and thus be forced to neglect the first one; nor when he has just returned from a cult ceremony, lest his recent contact with the cult spirits harm the woman" (Whiting, 1941:126).

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required castration.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required fasting.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– Yes

Notes: In order for men to enter into the yam cult and perform religious activities and learn ritual secrets, they must first go through an initiation ceremony during adolescence. "The whole subtribe participates in the age-grade ceremony, and all the boys from every hamlet who answer the call go through the rite together. The initiates gather in the early afternoon and march to a stream at the foot of the ridge. Each initiate is then chosen by an unrelated man who has already completed the cycle, and who thereby becomes the boy's ceremonial father. This older man slashes the tongue and penis of his ceremonial son, and then rubs salt or ashes in the wounds" (Whiting, 1941:66).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required time sacrifices.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Tattoos/scarification:

– Yes

Notes: In order for men to enter into the yam cult and perform religious activities and learn ritual secrets, they must first go through an initiation ceremony during adolescence. "The whole subtribe participates in the age-grade ceremony, and all the boys from every hamlet who answer the call go through the rite together. The initiates gather in the early afternoon and march to a stream at the foot of the ridge. Each initiate is then chosen by an unrelated

man who has already completed the cycle, and who thereby becomes the boy's ceremonial father. This older man slashes the tongue and penis of his ceremonial son, and then rubs salt or ashes in the wounds" (Whiting, 1941:66). "A kwoma boy becomes an adult when he receives the keloids which are a symbol of manhood. The scarification ceremony occurs when he has grown to full stature and is ready to marry... Each boy, when his turn comes, lies on a sago spathe. While the father of his future wife holds his hands, a special operator incises two semicircular cuts above each nipple and rubs ashes into them to make a raised scar" (Whiting, 1941:106). Similarly, "A girl enters adulthood in a slightly different and less public manner. She also is cut with other girls of her age, to each of whom she becomes a friend; but the operation takes place at the dwelling of the operator, instead of the house tamberan, and the design of her keloid is an elaborate circular figure centered about the navel" (Whiting, 1941:106).

Archaic ritual language:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A tribe

Notes: The Kwoma tribe has four distinct sub-tribes which occasionally band together in times of war or conflict, but have no political organization uniting the four sub-tribes (Whiting, 1941:5). "Each subtribe is divided into several hamlets, most of which are clustered about a 'house tamberan' or men's ceremonial lodge" (Whiting, 1941:6). Hamlets of a subtribe come together for age grade ceremonies and religious cult activities (Whiting, 1941:75). Additionally, the Kwoma have no political authority beyond the local community, which is reflective of autonomous bands and villages (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004). However, Murdock and Wilson (1972; Column 10: Descent), indicates that "the principal consanguineal kin groups are based on patrilineal descent...[and] the majority of the adult members belonging to the less mobile sex reside in the focal or typical community and constitute a minority of all adults of that sex in the community, as in the case of small localized lineages."

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of formal education.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: The Kwoma do not have a formal bureaucracy.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20 (food storage) indicates that food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: It can be assumed that transportation infrastructure is not present, as routes of land transport are "unimproved trails", according to Murdock and Morrow (1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004; SCCS Variable 14).

Taxation

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: "Since the period in which the Kwoma have been 'under control' has been so short, the government as yet does not make them pay a head tax" (Whiting and Reed, 1938:176).

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: "The belief in sorcery, as well as furnishing an explanation for sickness, functions as a means of social control. It stands, indeed, in lieu of a police force and strong political organization as a preventive of criminal behavior" (Whiting, 1941:219). Tuden and Marshall (1972) column 10, Police (note, equivalent to SCCS variable 90, Police) indicates that "police functions are not specialized or institutionalized at any level of political integration, the maintenance of law and order being left exclusively to informal mechanisms of social control, to private retaliation, or to sorcery."

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: As exemplified in Whiting, 1941:20, the Kwoma interact with the Australian police from the government station at Ambunti.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: According to Tuden and Marshall, 1972, (column 9, judiciary), indicates that "supreme judicial authority is lacking at any level above that the local community."

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: Because there is no formal social control among the Kwoma, it can be assumed that there is no formal legal code. Additionally, no ethnographic evidence indicates that a formal legal code is present.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: Whiting and Reed, 1938:178

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: "The lunar cycle is recognized but forms the basis of only a rude and relatively unimportant method of recording time" (Whiting and Reed, 1938:191).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The Kwoma are primarily horticulturalists, with a secondary dependence on gathering. Fishing and animal husbandry supplement the diet. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232. For an ethnographic description of Kwoma subsistence technologies, see Whiting and Reed, 1938:179-183.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: The Kwoma are primarily horticulturalists, with a secondary dependence on gathering. Fishing and animal husbandry supplement the diet. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232. For an

ethnographic description of Kwoma subsistence technologies, see Whiting and Reed, 1938:179-183.